

etc.) that have their own genetic material.

The aleurone grains may be regarded as a specific type of plastids (alongside with chloroplasts, chromoplasts, amyloplasts, proteoplasts, etc.). □

Genetic diversity in rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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Divergence analysis was performed to identify diverse genotypes for hybridization and to generate crosses that give transgressive segregants in later generations.

The parental divergence study used varieties released in Mekong Delta. Materials came from IRRI (21), India (3), Korea (1), Sri Lanka (1), and Vietnam (6).

The experiment was conducted at Omon in 1989 dry season, with 32 treatments in a randomized block design with three replications. Plots were 10 m², spacing was 15 × 20 cm.

Clustering (Mahalonobis D² statistics) was based on plant height, days to 50% flowering, panicle length, grains per panicle, unfilled grain percentage, effective tillers per plant, grain weight, and grain yield.

Table 1. Varieties partitioned into clusters on the basis of eight characters. Omon, Vietnam, 1989 dry season.

Cluster	Varieties
I	OM576, IR13240-10-1, IR25588-7-3-1, IR31868-64-2, IR19728, IR66, IR31802-48-2, OM296, IR17433-641-1, IR36, IR17434, IR9782-111-2, OM91, IR1352, IR39357-133-3, IR65, IR64, IR74, IR9129-192-2, IR21015-80-3, OM201, IR13240-10-1, OM620, IR4265-269-4-2
II	IR42, OM80, Bharain, Basmati 370 (mutant)
III	A69-1, IR48
IV	IR68
V	Basmati 370

Table 2. Average intracluster and intercluster D²-values, showing divergence of variety clusters. Omon, Vietnam, 1989 dry season.

Cluster	I	II	III	IV	V
I	7.1751	14.6391	16.5844	19.6446	21.3976
II		9.0341	15.7413	23.3252	14.0877
III			8.9537	10.9978	21.4578
IV				0.0000	27.1334
V					0.0000

The materials were grouped into five clusters by Tocher's method (Table 1). Clusters separated by the largest statistical distance (D²) show the maximum divergence (Table 2).

Plant height (frequency 8-43%) and days to 50% flowering (frequency 7-37%) contributed to divergence the most. □

Yield potential

Effect on rice yield of root damage to seedlings

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During droughts, uprooting of rice seedlings is difficult particularly in clay soils. Seedlings sustain severe root damage, in extreme cases losing almost all their roots. We evaluated the effect of different levels of root damage on yield in a field experiment during 1986 ahu (autumn). Six varieties and four levels of seedling root damage were

used in a split-plot design with three replications (see table). Plot size was 4 m².

Seedlings were pulled at 25 d after seeding and transplanted 29 May, 1 seedling/hill at 15- × 20-cm spacing. No fertilizer was applied.

There was no interaction between variety and root damage for any of the characters considered (see table). Seedlings with 50% roots removed did not differ from seedlings with intact roots in survival, yield attributes, and yield, but they flowered earlier. Seedlings with 98% roots removed by cutting at the bottom nodes and

Effect of seedling root damage and variety on yield, yield components, hill mortality, and flowering duration of rice. Titabar, India, 1986 autumn.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Hill mortality ^a (%)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)	Days to 50% flowering
<i>Seedling root damage</i>					
Intact roots	2.4	24	287.1	0.88	92
50% removed	2.2	24	310.3	0.71	90
98% removed	1.7	35	232.2	0.78	94
100% removed	0.4	69	67.4	0.50	98
LSD (0.05)	0.4	7	40.4	0.20	1
<i>Variety</i>					
Pusa 2-21	1.9	38	201.5	0.81	96
IET6155	2.2	30	268.6	0.79	102
IET6148	1.6	32	230.5	0.70	100
IET7983	1.6	42	217.7	0.77	94
IET7617	1.5	46	204.9	0.67	90
Culture 1	1.3	39	222.5	0.56	80
LSD (0.05)	0.4	9	ns	ns	2

^aAngular transformed data.

seedlings with all roots removed by cutting at ground level showed increased mortality and yield reduction. Seedlings with 98% roots removed could be used at higher numbers/hill to counteract hill mortality.

IET6155 and IET6148 had significantly lower hill mortality under all levels of root damage, indicating their ability for quick establishment. □

Source-sink relationship at postflowering of rices under low light stress

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We screened cultivars for tolerance for low light during ripening and assessed

the source-sink relationship. Seedlings (25 d old) of 15 early- and medium-duration rice varieties were transplanted at 10- × 10-cm spacing. Four uniform tillers/hill were selected at flowering. Five hills each were subjected to normal light and low light (50% normal), with two replications. The desired light intensity was obtained by covering the rice canopy with a wooden screen fitted on iron frames and adjusting the distance between the slats.

Data on shade index (ratio of grain yield under low and normal light) indicate variation in varietal response (see table). Under low light, Co 41, Archana, Jalgaon 5, and Ptb 10 showed about 50% yield reduction. Other varieties had higher yield reductions. Shading during ripening increased sterility and decreased 1,000-grain weight. Ratna, Pusa 33, Indira, and

Pallavi had more than 85% sterility.

The product of leaf area and solar radiation or leaf area and photosynthetic rate at flowering was taken as the source of carbohydrate. The product of spikelet number and test weight was taken as the sink.

The correlation between source and sink under normal light was positive and significant ($r = 0.76^{**a}$ and 0.64^{**b}), resulting in good correlation between source and grain yield ($r = 0.54^*$). Those relationships were observed under low light.

Under low light, the association between stem weight ratio at flowering and yield was positive ($r = 0.72^{**}$). The stem losses were higher under low light.

The balance of source and sink under natural light appears to be disturbed under low light stress, causing more stem loss. □

Influence of low light during ripening on yield and yield characters of 15 rice varieties. CRR, India.

Variety	Yield ^a (g)		Shading index	Grain no.		Stem loss (g) (flowering-harvest)		Sterility (%)		1000-grain wt (g)	
	100% light	50% light		Normal light	Low light	Normal light	Low light	Normal light	Low light	Normal light	Low light
	Pusa 33	14.3		1.6	11	787	114	2.38	4.02	67.9	91.5
Co 41	13.4	7.9	59	764	546	0.42	4.71	53.8	58.0	17.5	14.4
Cauvery	11.7	4.2	36	572	281	0.47	6.25	71.7	73.0	20.4	14.9
Saket 4	12.2	3.8	31	611	231	0.92	3.24	57.3	76.6	19.9	16.2
Jalgaon 5	14.4	7.3	51	680	375	2.14	10.48	72.9	77.5	21.1	19.4
Ratna	11.1	0.8	9	628	55	5.36	6.48	61.8	93.0	17.7	15.1
ADT32	25.0	8.7	35	1206	546	2.21	3.38	42.5	62.6	20.7	15.8
Karikalan	17.6	7.5	43	742	364	2.40	8.38	34.7	51.8	23.7	20.6
Swarnaprabha	18.8	7.7	41	793	348	8.56	14.14	64.7	65.1	23.8	22.1
Ptb 10	19.3	9.2	47	771	388	5.30	8.57	29.6	62.2	25.1	23.7
Indira	11.3	2.0	17	551	136	1.68	3.57	70.4	86.2	20.5	14.5
CR157-190	14.5	3.1	22	683	176	4.08	7.28	63.8	83.1	21.3	17.8
Archana	11.2	6.4	58	569	369	5.32	9.90	65.1	70.5	19.7	17.5
IR36	15.7	3.9	25	725	219	1.01	4.79	59.0	80.0	21.6	17.6
Pallavi	12.8	2.3	18	635	140	1.02	1.73	55.9	87.5	20.1	16.2
Mean	14.9	5.1	33	714	286	2.88	6.48	58.1	74.6	20.8	17.8
LSD (0.05)											
Variety (V)	1.2		9	19		0.70		1.5		0.7	
Shading (S)	0.4			7		0.25		0.6		0.3	
V × S	1.7			27		0.99		2.2		1.0	

^aFrom 20 tillers.

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